

Kuala Lumpur International Invention & Innovation Symposium

1 January 2024 – 30 June 2024

Kuala Lumpur International Invention & Innovation Symposium

Online/Virtual Edition

KL3IS 2024

“Technology For the Future”

Powered By DIGIT360 Sdn Bhd – UiTM Startup Company

<https://kl3is.com>

<https://t.me/kl3is.com>

<https://t.me/digit360hq>

<https://registro.kl3is.com>

What is KL3IS?

“Technology For the Future”

Our Vision

KL3IS is an *international invention and innovation symposium* that feature improvement, modification, and development of a new product, idea, services, teaching, and etc,

Our Mission

KL3IS strive to *offer participants a recognition of their effort, invention, and innovation via virtual and interactive platform*. All submission and judging process will be conducted via online platform; in the comfort of your own places.

What to Expect?

“Technology For the Future”

**WE MAKE
IMPOSSIBLE
TO BE
POSSIBLE**

Recognition

Achieve recognition for your invention, innovation, product, or services!

Peers' Learning

Learn from experience of others.

Exposure

Get rewards for your career advancement.

KL3IS Timeline

“Technology For the Future”

Registration

1 January 2024 – 30 June 2024

Deadline

30 June 2024, 11.59 PM
(Malaysian Time GMT +8)

Judging

July 2024

Awards Ceremony

31 July 2024

KL3IS Poster

“Technology For the Future”

“Technology for the future”

Kuala Lumpur *Online* International Invention
Invention & Innovation Symposium

Registration: 1 January 2024 - 30 June 2024 Judging: July 2024 Awards: August 2024

Knowledge Sharing Project Exposure Gain Recognition

Digitally organized by:

digit360 UTM Startup Company DIGIT360 UNIVERSITI TEKNOLOGI MARA Cawangan Kelantan

REGISTER NOW ➔

More Info kl3is.com Register <https://registro.kl3is.com>

Telegram Support <https://t.me/kl3is> DIGIT360 Events <https://t.me/digit360hq>
<https://events.digit360.com.my>

KL3IS Fee & Category

"Technology For the Future"

Category & Fee

Prodigy

- ✓ Primary School
- ✓ Secondary School
- ✓ eCertificate
- ✓ Medal x 1 Unit

RM **50** /project

International USD 50

[SIGN UP](#)

Futurist

- ✓ Tertiary Students
- ✓ University
- ✓ College
- ✓ eCertificate
- ✓ Medal x 1 Unit

RM **100** /project

International USD 80

[SIGN UP](#)

Ideator

- ✓ Professionals
- ✓ Teacher
- ✓ Lecturer
- ✓ eCertificate
- ✓ Medal x 1 Unit

RM **150** /project

International USD 100

[SIGN UP](#)

KL3IS Organizers

“Technology For the Future”

KL3IS How to Register?

“Technology For the Future”

Step 1

- Register new account at <https://registro.kl3is.com>

Step 2

- Login using email (username) and password.

Step 3

- Click ‘New Project’ to create new submission.
- Submit

Step 4

- New project will be available at dashboard.
- Click ‘Pay Now’ to confirm the payment.

Step 5

- Prepare presentation video.
- Video duration is 6 minutes to 10 minutes

Step 6

- Upload video to your YouTube channel.
- Set permission to either Public or unlisted.

Step 7

- Click ‘Upload Video’ in Registro and paste the YouTube Video URL.
- Submit

Step 8 (Optional)

- Optional – you may submit additional documents if necessary – such as copyright, certs, patent, testimony, etc.
- Upload to Google Drive and set permission to ‘Anyone can View’

KL3IS Rules & Regulation

“Technology For the Future”

Maximum of 8 members per project

Video duration in 6 minutes and 30 seconds

Upload video to YouTube

Futurist Category must be led by student

Prodigy Category must be lead by student

All results is non-negotiable

KL3IS Video Content

“Technology For the Future”

Innovation and Creativity:

- The award-winning invention should showcase a high level of innovation and creativity. It should demonstrate a unique and inventive solution to a problem or a groundbreaking improvement upon existing technologies.

Significance and Impact:

- The invention should have significant potential for impact and contribute to advancements in its respective field or industry. It should address a critical need, solve a pressing problem, or offer substantial improvements over existing solutions.

Technical Excellence:

- The award recipient should demonstrate technical excellence in the development and implementation of the invention. The invention should showcase a deep understanding of the underlying principles and exhibit exceptional technical skill in its design, functionality, and operation.

Practical Applicability:

- The invention should have practical applicability and demonstrate the potential for real-world implementation. It should possess the necessary features, scalability, and adaptability to be effectively deployed in relevant contexts.

KL3IS Video Content

“Technology For the Future”

Market Potential and Commercial Viability:

- The award-winning invention should exhibit market potential and commercial viability. It should demonstrate potential demand, marketability, and feasibility for commercialization. Factors such as market analysis, business models, and potential partnerships or investment opportunities may be considered.

Scientific Rigor:

- The invention should be grounded in sound scientific principles and methodologies. It should demonstrate rigorous research, experimentation, and evidence-based approaches in its development and validation.

Intellectual Property Protection:

- The inventor should have taken appropriate measures to protect their intellectual property rights. Documentation and evidence of patent filings, copyrights, or other relevant intellectual property protection should be provided.

Presentation and Communication:

- The quality of the presentation and communication of the invention is crucial. The award recipient should effectively and compellingly communicate the value, impact, and potential of their invention through clear and engaging presentations, documentation, and visual aids.

Ethical Considerations:

- The invention should adhere to ethical standards and considerations. It should not involve any illegal or harmful activities and should align with principles of social responsibility and sustainability.

Originality and Uniqueness:

- The award-winning invention should exhibit originality and uniqueness. It should differentiate itself from existing solutions or demonstrate significant improvements upon previous inventions.

KL3IS Medal

“Technology For the Future”

**THANK YOU
AND
SEE YOU
NEXT TIME**

